

Analysis of Common Problems and Treatment Methods of Diaphragm Wall

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Abstract: *in recent years, with the increase of foundation depth of high-rise buildings, Metro and various large underground buildings, as well as the limitation of surrounding environment and construction site, diaphragm wall has gradually replaced the traditional construction method as an effective means of deep foundation construction. Taking the reinforced concrete diaphragm wall with trough slab as the research object, this paper expounds and analyses the technical key points and difficulties in each construction process of diaphragm wall, and puts forward some corresponding solutions, which can be used as a reference for the construction of diaphragm wall in China.*

Key-words: *Diaphragm wall; Treatment methods; drill bit*

1. Introduction:

The construction of diaphragm wall refers to the construction process of using trenching equipment on the ground, excavating a long and narrow trench along the periphery of deep excavation project under the action of mud wall protection, placing reinforcement cages in the trench and pouring concrete to build a section of reinforced concrete wall.

The technical classification of diaphragm wall is complex. It can be divided into PILE-ROW type, trough-plate type and combination type according to the way of wall-forming. According to the excavation situation, diaphragm wall and diaphragm wall can be divided into three types: PILE-ROW type, trough-plate type and combination type. The diaphragm wall has many advantages, such as high stiffness, retaining soil and water, no vibration and low noise during construction. It can be used in any soil construction, but the construction cost is high and the technology is complex.

In recent years, with the increase of foundation depth of high-rise buildings, Metro and various large underground buildings, as well as the limitation of surrounding environment and construction site, diaphragm wall has gradually replaced the traditional construction method as an effective means of deep foundation construction. Taking the reinforced concrete diaphragm wall with trough slab as the research object, this paper expounds and analyses the technical points and difficulties in each construction procedure of diaphragm wall, and puts forward the corresponding solutions, which can be used as a reference for the construction of diaphragm wall in China. ^[1]

2. Common problems of drill bit and their solutions

During the construction of diaphragm wall, there are many kinds of problems related to drill bits, but the most common problems are paste drilling, sticking drilling and rig drilling. The most commonly used treatment methods are as follows.

(1) Paste drill

It is the phenomenon that clay adheres to the drill bit because of too much mud and too fast footage when drilling in the clay layer. When paste drilling occurs, the drill bit can be raised into the groove, the clay on the drill bit can be removed, and the groove hole can be cleaned up after slag treatment before drilling.

(2) sticking

The common sticking conditions are as follows:

(a) The drilling stops too long in the middle of drilling, and the mud deposits on the top of the bit and the bit is jammed. In order to avoid this situation, the bit should be lifted or lowered from time to time in the drilling process to avoid sludge deposition or blockage of groove holes. At the same time, it should be diligent in slag cleaning. When it is necessary to stop drilling halfway, the bit should be put out of the groove.

B) The drill bit is stuck in an underground obstacle. When obstacles are found in the drilling process, obstacles should be dealt with first to ensure that obstacles are removed before drilling continues.

C) The hole wall of the groove collapsed and the drill bit was jammed. To avoid collapse, while strictly controlling the proportion of mud, it is necessary to avoid the collision between the lifting bit and the groove wall as far as possible, so as to reduce the chances of soft wall soil collapse.

(3) Drilling rig

When the used bit is worn seriously and the diameter of the bit is reduced, the width of the groove hole will be reduced. When the new bit with qualified diameter is replaced and drilling continues, the new bit fails to reach the depth that the old bit has already drilled. This phenomenon is called drilling support. In order to avoid this situation, the diameter and dimension of the bit should be checked regularly during the drilling process, and the qualified new bit should be replaced in time when severe wear of the bit is found.²¹

3. Common drilling quality problems and their solutions

In the construction process of diaphragm wall, how to drill hole quality has a great influence on the construction progress. Among them, the quality problems easily occur are plum blossom hole, oblique hole and blind hole. The following is a brief description of these phenomena and their common treatment methods.

(1) Plum blossom pore

When drilling hard rock or drilling concrete at phase I-II joints and using non-circular bits (such as cross bits or word bits), it is easy to see that the bits can only be lifted from a single direction (rather than from any direction) to return to the original depth. This phenomenon is called plum blossom hole. In order to avoid this phenomenon, the bit should be lifted and drilled in different directions from time to time in the process of drilling.

(2) oblique hole

Oblique holes are more likely to occur at stage I-II joints or when hard obstacles are encountered. In this case, the drilling speed should be slowed down, and the perpendicularity of the hole position should be checked regularly to ensure that the hard material has been removed or the hole position is normal before drilling.

(3) Blind hole

The so-called blind hole is the phenomenon that the drilling stops too long in the process of drilling, and the mud deposits in the hole, blocking the hole. In order to avoid blind holes, slag cleaning should be carried out before stopping drilling, and stopping drilling time should be shortened as far as possible. In addition, the collapse of the groove wall is also the cause of blind holes, so the collapse of the groove wall should be avoided when making holes^[3]

4. Causes of Cage Dropping Difficulty and Its Treatment

There are many reasons for the difficulty of falling into cage, among which the most common reasons and

treatment methods are:

A) The size of the reinforcing cage is not accurate, and the cage width is larger than the slot width and can not be placed. When designing the shape of reinforcing cage in slot section, the width of reinforcing cage should be 200-300 mm smaller than that of slot section, so that there is a gap between the reinforcing cage and both ends. The manufacturing dimension of reinforcing cage in stage II groove section should be based on the actual width between two stages I groove sections measured in situ.

B) When the steel cage is hoisted, it will bend and be unable to enter the groove. Because of the heavy weight of steel cage, two cranes are usually used to lift the steel cage by crossbeam or hanger combined with the lifting method of main and auxiliary hooks.

C) Segmented steel cage cannot be grooved because the upper and lower sections are not connected directly. If the reinforcing cage is made in segments, the lower reinforcing cage should be vertically hung on the guide wall for a long time, then the upper reinforcing cage should be vertically lifted, and the upper and lower reinforcing cages should be welded in a straight line.

D) The groove wall is uneven or curved, which prevents the reinforcement cage from entering the groove. In the process of drilling, the verticality of each hole position should be tested, and the deviation of the hole position along the groove section and the vertical groove section should meet the requirements. The oblique hole should be corrected before the next working procedure can be carried out^[4]

5. Causes and treatment of 4-groove wall collapse

Slot wall collapse is also common in the construction of diaphragm wall. There are many reasons for the collapse of the groove wall, and the treatment methods are also different. Among them, the common landslides and treatment methods are as follows:

A) The slurry density and concentration are not enough to protect the groove wall, resulting in the collapse of the groove wall. In order to avoid such problems, the key is to select suitable mud according to geological conditions. When encountering soft soil or quicksand layer, the mud density should be increased appropriately. In general, the mud viscosity is 19-25s and the relative density is less than 112.

B) In soft soil or sand, the drilling speed is too fast or the drill bit collides with the hole wall of the groove and causes the collapse. In order to avoid such problems, attention should be paid to controlling the footage speed, not too fast or idle for a long time, and try to avoid the collision of the drill bit with the hole wall.

C) The groundwater level is too high or confined water appears in the hole, which causes the collapse of the groove wall. In order to solve this problem, mud density and liquid level elevation should be adjusted in time according to drilling conditions. The liquid level of groove pit should be at least 500 mm higher than that of groundwater, so as to ensure the hydraulic pressure of mud and the differential pressure of groundwater, so as to achieve the goal of controlling the stability of groove wall. In order to prevent the influence of Rainstorm on mud, the guide wall is 200 mm higher than the ground, and the surface drainage ditches and catchment wells are laid at the same time^[5].

D) The length of the slot is too long, and it takes too long to complete a slot, which causes the hole to collapse due to the long shelf time and mud precipitation. In order to avoid this problem, it is necessary to shorten the time required to complete a single slot according to the geological conditions and construction capacity, and considering the construction period. The length of the trough section is 3-4 m in areas with high groundwater level, silty sand and easy to collapse. After grooving, steel cages should be hoisted in time and underwater concrete should be poured.

E) Groove collapse is caused by excessive additional load on the groove surface. In order to avoid this

problem, the dynamic and static loads of heavy objects and large machinery should be avoided as far as possible near the construction trough. The lifting equipment of steel cage should be as far away from the trough edge as possible. Roadbed and thick steel plate can also be used to diffuse pressure. When serious landslides occur in the above-mentioned cases, high-quality clay can be filled into the groove to 2-3 m above the groove hole position, and then re-pore after the deposition is compact.

6. Floating cage and Its treatment

Floating cage is also a common phenomenon in the construction process, combined with the actual causes of floating cage, different treatment methods are given.

A) The steel cage is too light to float when pouring concrete. The light reinforcing cage can be welded and fixed at anchorage points on the guide wall.

B) When concrete is poured, the depth of the pipe is too deep to make the reinforcing cage float. When pouring concrete, the embedding depth of the conduit is generally controlled at 2-4 m, less than 1 m is prone to leak-out accidents, and more than 6 m is prone to the failure of the conduit to be pulled out.

C) The steel cage floats because of the rapid pouring of concrete. In this case, the speed of concrete pouring should be slowed down, even stop pouring for 10 to 15 minutes, and then continue pouring after the reinforcement cage is stabilized.

7. Treatment Measures of Concrete Reverse Slurry Irregularity

A) Deformation of the catheter or blockage of foreign body make the water plug fail to rush out of the bottom of the catheter and result in the failure of reverse slurry. When installing the catheter, the quality of the catheter should be carefully checked. No deformed or damaged catheter should be used. Clean water is used to wash the catheter every time the catheter is disassembled or installed to ensure smooth inner wall of the catheter.

B) The excessive thickness of sediment in the groove leads to the failure of shear plug counter-slurry. After clearing holes and placing reinforcing steel cages, the thickness of sediment in the groove holes should be measured to determine that the sediment should be poured into concrete within the allowable range.

C) When concrete is poured into the vicinity of the top of the guide wall, due to the decrease of the pressure in the conduit, the concrete in the conduit is not easy to flow out. At this time, the irrigation speed should be slowed down and the depth of the tube should be reduced, but not less than 1 m. At the same time, it should be supplemented by pulling the catheter up and down, but the pulling range should not be too large, so as to avoid pulling the catheter out of the concrete surface.

8. Treatment Measures of Concrete Reverse Slurry Irregularity

(1) The pipe joint is not tight or the pipe is damaged. The mud seeps into the pipe and causes the wall to be muddy. The conduit joint shall be sealed with rubber rings and tightly connected with thick thread fasteners. Check the integrity of the catheter carefully during installation to prevent the use of damaged catheters.

(2) When shearing plug, the first batch of concrete is insufficient to bury the outlet of the bottom of the conduit, resulting in mud inclusion in the wall. The initial grouting quantity of concrete should ensure that the depth of concrete embedded in the conduit is not less than 0.15 m after concrete filling, so that the pressure of concrete inside the conduit and mud outside the conduit can be balanced. When the initial

concrete is sufficient, the shear plug can be used to irrigate. The initial grouting quantity of concrete can be calculated according to relevant formulas.

(3) The paving area of the catheter is insufficient, and part of the catheter cannot be filled with mud. In the unit groove section, the distance between the catheter and both ends of the groove section should not be greater than 115 m, and the distance between the two catheters should not be greater than 3 m.

(4) The depth of the conduit is not enough, and the sludge enters the concrete from the bottom. When pouring concrete, the conduit should always be buried in the concrete. It is strictly forbidden to put the conduit on the concrete surface. The minimum embedding depth of the catheter should not be less than 1 m. When it is found that the bottom of the conduit is lifted off the concrete surface due to the detection of the error of the concrete surface or the excessive lifting of the conduit, the position of the original concrete surface can be accurately measured, and the conduit can be reinstalled immediately, so that the distance between the conduit and the concrete surface is 3-5 m, and the water-proof plug is installed to re-cut and pour the concrete, which is commonly referred to as the secondary shear plug.

9. Treatment Measures for Serious Slope Wall Collapse in Concrete Irrigation

If the amount of concrete pouring is not large when the collapse occurs, the steel cage should be lifted, the concrete should be cleared out and re-cleared, and then the steel cage and conduit should be installed to pour concrete. If part of the concrete has been consolidated during the collapse, it is impossible to pull out the reinforcing cage. In this case, the concrete can only be continuously poured out, and then the mud layer can be treated by grouting reinforcement.

10. Conclusion

In a word, the construction of diaphragm wall is a complicated construction process with high technical requirements. In the construction process, we should strengthen technical management and improve the quality of workers. We should have a full understanding of the possible quality problems. Only by taking corresponding preventive and treatment measures, summing up experience and strengthening the prevention of common quality defects, can we shorten the construction period, reduce the cost of construction and ensure the quality of the project.

Above eight aspects of the problems often encountered in the construction of diaphragm wall are analyzed, hoping to provide some help and reference for technical personnel in this industry.

11. References

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